

PARALLEL COMPUTING AND DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: A model for the damage's evolution in composite materials is here proposed. It consists in a microscopic/macroscopic approach requiring the solution of two uncoupled steps. The first one consists in the computation of the composite's homogeneous equivalent behaviors, damaged by defects postulated at the microscopic composite's level. The second, consists then in solving a nonlinear, time-dependent, macroscopic problem.

These steps require unfortunately a lot of computations whose numerical costs may be prohibitive. It is here proposed to reduce them, thanks to the development of a strategy allowing to take benefit from the parallel computers performances.

Starting from two three-dimensional, industrially-realistic examples, one shows that this methodology may be fruitful if one knows how to choose a subdomain decomposition, taking in account the damages and the heterogeneities of the composite's representative volume element.

KEYWORDS: damage, thermoelasticity, homogenization, subdomain decomposition techniques, parallelism

INTRODUCTION

This paper deals with the simulation of damage's propagation in composite structures. To this way we use an homogenization technique which leads to a microscopic/macroscopic approach. To this purpose we first postulate damage criteria in the composite representative volume element. These criteria introduce parameters which are chosen as microscopic damage parameters. The use of the homogenization technique, allows then to construct a damaged macroscopic medium model, based on a microscopic approach of a body weakened by microdefects. The damage's evolution may be then modelled and computed inside an adjusted thermodynamic framework.

Unfortunately this methodology requires a lot of computations, required for the construction of composite homogenized behaviors connected to each of its microscopic damaged configuration. In addition to the three-dimensional geometry, a good description of the damage process needs the choice of a lot of microscopic damage parameters and a lot of values for these parameters. Thus, this methodology requires large computer CPU times and large memory spaces, and comes up against the limitations prescribed by the actual computers technology.

A way to get round these overcosts consists in using multiprocessor computers. We propose thus in this communication to show how one can use homogenization techniques and substructuring techniques to take advantage of the parallel computers performances.

In order to assess the benefit of this methodology, we consider two kinds of three-dimensional composites, used at the industrial level as covering materials for aeronautical engines. The first one is made up of glass microballoons coated in a resin (syntactic foams). The observed damage process of this composite consists of the implosion of the balloons. The second example concerns sewed layers of unidirectional composites. Due to the different expansion coefficients of these materials, when the structure undergoes a high temperature increase, damage occurs under the form of delaminations between constituents.

A MODEL FOR DAMAGE'S EVOLUTION SIMULATION IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

In order to simulate the damage's evolution in composite structures, we use hereafter a microscopic/macroscopic approach of a macroscopic medium weakened by microdefects. To this purpose we classically consider two scales: the microscopic scale is attached to the representative volume element of the composite and is thus representative of microscopic effects such damages; its basis is denoted by $(0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$; at the macroscopic level any point of the structure is marked with respect of a system of axis denoted by $(0, x_1, x_2, x_3)$.

This approach consists first in postulating damages at the microscopic level. The connected damaged homogeneous behavior laws are then computed thanks to the homogenization principle. In order to simulate the damage's evolution in the composite structures under consideration, it remains lastly to solve, at the macroscopic level, a nonlinear, time-dependent problem .

Computation of Homogenized Damaged Behaviors

We consider in what follows that the composite under consideration admits a geometric and mechanic periodicity, such that this material may be defined by the knowledge of its period or basic cell, denoted by Y . In order to describe the damage's evolution in this material, let us consider its basic cell as a real structure containing defects, as for example stress-free holes (denoted by C). Let us associate to these defects, parameters, denoted in vectorial notations by D . Thanks to the homogenization process for periodic media [1], [2], one can associate to this microscopic description of the damaged composite material a homogeneous equivalent behavior. To this way and when a thermo-elastic behavior for the constituents is chosen, we have to find the microscopic deviation in temperature τ and the microscopic displacement field u , solutions in the elastic part of Y (denoted by Y^*) to the following problems, also known as cellular problems [3], [4]:

Elasticity cellular problem:

$$(1) \quad \begin{cases} \operatorname{div}_y \boldsymbol{\sigma} = 0, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{a} [\mathbf{e}(\mathbf{u}) - \boldsymbol{\alpha} (T - T_0)] & \text{in } Y^* \\ \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{E} \mathbf{y} \text{ Y-periodic}, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{n}) \text{ Y-antiperiodic} \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{n}) = 0 \text{ on } \partial C, \quad \langle\langle \mathbf{e}(\mathbf{u}) \rangle\rangle_Y = \mathbf{E} \end{cases}$$

Thermal conduction cellular problem:

$$(2) \quad \begin{cases} \operatorname{div}_y \mathbf{q} = 0, \quad \mathbf{q} = -\boldsymbol{\lambda} \nabla_y \tau & \text{in } Y^* \\ \tau - \mathbf{F} \mathbf{y} \text{ Y-periodic}, \quad \mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{n} \text{ Y-antiperiodic} \\ \mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \text{ on } \partial C, \quad \langle\langle \nabla_y \tau \rangle\rangle_Y = \mathbf{F} \cdot \end{cases}$$

In these problems div_y and ∇_y respectively denote the divergence and gradient operators with respect to the microscopic coordinates y . We have also used the following notations:

$$(3) \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{e}(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2} (\nabla_y \mathbf{u} + {}^t\nabla_y \mathbf{u}), \quad \langle\langle \nabla_y f \rangle\rangle_Y = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_{\partial Y} f \mathbf{n} \, dS \\ \phi \text{ Y-periodic} \Leftrightarrow \phi \text{ admits the same value at points belonging to opposite faces of } Y \end{cases}$$

and respectively denoted by λ , \mathbf{a} , $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$, ρ , c the conduction, stiffness, expansion tensors, the mass density and the specific heat, and introduced the fields \mathbf{E} , \mathbf{F} , T which represent the macroscopic strain tensor, the macroscopic temperature gradient tensor and the macroscopic temperature (T_0 is the reference macroscopic temperature).

Once these problems have been solved, one may then construct the damaged homogenized behavior sought, through the computation of the stiffness, conduction and expansion homogenized tensors $\mathbf{Q}^h(\mathbf{D})$, $\boldsymbol{\lambda}^h(\mathbf{D})$, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^h(\mathbf{D})$ which connect the microscopic fields to the macroscopic ones by the relations:

$$(4) \quad \begin{cases} \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle_Y = \boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \mathbf{Q}^h(\mathbf{D}) \mathbf{E} - \mathbf{Q}^h(\mathbf{D}) \boldsymbol{\alpha}^h(\mathbf{D}) (T - T_0) \\ \langle \mathbf{q} \rangle_Y = \mathbf{S} = -\boldsymbol{\lambda}^h(\mathbf{D}) \mathbf{F} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{with } \langle f \rangle_Y = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_{Y^*} f(y) \, dy$$

and the homogenized specific heat denoted by $C^h(\mathbf{D})$.

Let us lastly specify that thanks to the linearity of these problems with respect to the macroscopic data (strain \mathbf{E} , temperature deviation $(T-T_0)$, temperature gradient \mathbf{F}) the solutions to problems (1) and (2) are usefully splitted in the following forms:

$$(5) \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}^{kh} E_{kh} + \mathbf{w} (T - T_0) & (k, h \in \{1, 2, 3\}) \quad (\text{with } \mathbf{u}^{kh} = \mathbf{u}^{hk} \text{ thanks to } E_{kh} = E_{hk}) \\ \tau = \tau^k F_k & (k \in \{1, 2, 3\}) \end{cases}$$

allowing to solve once and for all these problems, undependently from the macroscopic fields which have to be now computed.

Damage's Evolution

Once previous step has been carried out, one knows each of the homogenized equivalent behaviors of the composite material under consideration, corresponding to given values of the damage parameters considered at the microscopic level.

For a given thermo-mechanical loading prescribed to the composite structure (which occupies the volume Ω), the damage's evolution is then modelled by introducing the macroscopic free energy density defined by:

$$(6) \quad \langle \rho \rangle_Y \psi(\mathbf{E}, T, \mathbf{D}) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{E} \mathbf{Q}^h(\mathbf{D}) \mathbf{E} - \mathbf{Q}^h(\mathbf{D}) \boldsymbol{\alpha}^h(\mathbf{D}) \mathbf{E} (T - T_0) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\langle \rho \rangle_Y C^h(\mathbf{D})}{T_0} (T - T_0)^2$$

where the vector \mathbf{D} (n entries assumed) is constituted by the damage parameters.

The volume dissipation Δ is then given by:

$$(7) \quad \Delta = \sum_{i=1}^n F_i \frac{dD_i}{dt} - \frac{\mathbf{S}}{T} \nabla_x T$$

where we have denoted by F_i the thermodynamical damage force associated to the damage parameter D_i , defined by:

$$(8) \quad F_i = - \frac{\partial \{ \langle \rho \rangle_Y \psi(\mathbf{E}, T, \mathbf{D}) \}}{\partial D_i} \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

A useful means for satisfying the positivity of the dissipation (7) consists in using the thermodynamic framework of standard generalized materials [5]. Assuming the classical decoupling between the mechanical and thermal dissipations and starting from the existence of pseudo potentials of dissipation denoted by $\phi^{th}(\nabla_x T)$ and $\phi^{mec}(F_1, \dots, F_n)$ which are chosen as positive or zero functions, convex and zero in 0, this framework allows one to obtain the complementary laws under the forms:

$$(9) \quad \frac{\mathbf{S}}{T} = - \frac{\partial \phi^{th}(\nabla_x T)}{\partial (\nabla_x T)}, \quad \frac{dD_i}{dt} = \frac{\partial \phi^{mec}(F_1, \dots, F_n)}{\partial F_i} \quad (i = 1, \dots, n)$$

The choice of these potentials has to be *a posteriori* justified by collation of results with experimental data. In what follows we choose the thermal potential in order to obtain the

classical Fourier's law for the temperature. Concerning the mechanic potential, it may be for instance chosen as follows:

$$(10) \quad \phi^{mec}(F_1, \dots, F_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\alpha_i}{1 + \beta_i} |F_i|^{1 + \beta_i} \quad (\alpha_i > 0, \beta_i > 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\})$$

This particular choice leads to a damage's evolution law of Norton's kind [6].

Once these choices have been made the evolution of damages will be obtained by the solution of the following macroscopic problem:

$$(11) \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \operatorname{div}_x \Sigma = 0 & \text{in } \Omega \\ \Sigma = Q^h(\mathbf{D}) \mathbf{E} - Q^h(\mathbf{D}) \alpha^h(\mathbf{D}) (T - T_0) & \text{in } \Omega \\ 2 \mathbf{E} = \nabla_x \mathbf{u} + {}^t \nabla_x \mathbf{u} & \\ \langle \rho \rangle_Y C^h(\mathbf{D}) \frac{T}{T_0} \frac{dT}{dt} + \operatorname{div}_x \mathbf{S} = \sum_{i=1}^n (F_i - T \frac{\partial F_i}{\partial T}) \frac{dD_i}{dt} - Q^h(\mathbf{D}) \alpha^h(\mathbf{D}) T \frac{d\mathbf{E}}{dt} & \text{in } \Omega \\ \mathbf{S} = -\lambda^h(\mathbf{D}) \nabla_x T & \text{in } \Omega \\ \frac{dD_i}{dt} = \frac{\partial \phi^{mec}}{\partial F_i} & (i = 1, \dots, n) \quad \text{in } \Omega \end{array} \right.$$

for which it is required to specify boundary and initial conditions.

The damage's evolution may be thus computed in the two steps given above which consists in:

1. constructing the homogeneous equivalent damaged behaviors connected to chosen values of microscopic defects;
2. solving the macroscopic time-dependent problem describing the damages evolution.

THE SCHUR COMPLEMENT METHOD FOR THE SOLUTION OF CELLULAR PROBLEMS

The method explained above for the computation of damage's evolution in composite structures has been already successfully used for the study of damage by fibers breaks in unidirectional composites [7]. It requires however the solution of the cellular problems (1), (2) for each set of values of the damage parameters postulated at the composite's microscopic level. These computations may induce very large CPU times in the case where, like here, the geometry is three-dimensional. This is the reason why we have developed a parallel way for these solutions; it consists in using a subdomain decomposition technique (Schur complement method) and allows to take benefit from the parallel computers performances.

In order to present the application of this technique to the solution of cellular problems, let us consider the thermal cellular problems (2). Thanks to the decomposition (5) it may be easily shown that the fields τ^k are the solutions to the following problems:

$$(12) \quad \begin{cases} \operatorname{div}_y \mathbf{q}^k = 0, \quad q_j^k = -\lambda_{jk} - \lambda_{ji} \frac{\partial \tau^k}{\partial y_i} & \text{in } Y^* \\ \mathbf{q}^k \cdot \mathbf{n} \text{ Y-antiperiodic}, \quad \tau^k \text{ Y-periodic} \\ \mathbf{q}^k \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 & \text{on } \partial C \end{cases}$$

Let us then introduce a subdomain decomposition of Y into 2 subdomains (for reader's convenience), denoted by $(1)Y$ and $(2)Y$. We denote by Γ the common boundaries of these subdomains and the external boundary of Y (on which periodicity conditions for τ^k are prescribed).

Let us next introduce the fields $(i)\tau^k, (i)q^k$ solutions in the subdomain $(i)Y$ to the following problem:

$$(13) \quad \begin{cases} \operatorname{div}_y (i)\mathbf{q}^k = 0, \quad (i)q_j^k = -\lambda_{jk} - \lambda_{ji} \frac{\partial (i)\tau^k}{\partial y_i} & \text{in } (i)Y^* \\ (i)\tau^k = \mu & \text{on } \Gamma \cap \partial(i)Y \\ (i)\mathbf{q}^k \cdot (i)\mathbf{n} = 0 & \text{on } \partial C \end{cases}$$

where we have denoted by $(i)\mathbf{n}$ the unit outward normal to $\partial(i)Y$ and introduce the (not yet known) temperature field μ which has to be characterized.

These fields will coincide with the restrictions of τ^k and q^k in $(i)Y$ if and only if they satisfy the continuity of normal heat flux on Γ :

$$(14) \quad (1)\mathbf{q} \cdot (1)\mathbf{n} = (2)\mathbf{q} \cdot (2)\mathbf{n} \quad \text{on } \Gamma$$

In order to deduce the problem whose solution is μ , let us use the linearity of problem (13) and thus split its solution as follows:

$$(15) \quad (i)\tau^k = (i)\theta^k + (i)\omega^k, \quad (i)q^k = (i)\Theta^k + (i)\Omega^k$$

where $(i)\theta^k$ and $(i)\omega^k$ are the solutions to:

$$(16) \quad \begin{cases} \operatorname{div}_y {}^{(i)}\Theta^k = 0, \quad {}^{(i)}\Theta_j^k = -\lambda_{jk} - \lambda_{ji} \frac{\partial {}^{(i)}\theta^k}{\partial y_i} & \text{in } {}^{(i)}Y^* \\ {}^{(i)}\theta^k = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma \cap \partial {}^{(i)}Y \\ {}^{(i)}\Theta^k \cdot {}^{(i)}\mathbf{n} = 0 & \text{on } \partial C \end{cases}$$

$$(17) \quad \begin{cases} \operatorname{div}_y {}^{(i)}\Omega^k = 0, \quad {}^{(i)}\Omega_j^k = -\lambda_{ji} \frac{\partial {}^{(i)}\omega^k}{\partial y_i} & \text{in } {}^{(i)}Y^* \\ {}^{(i)}\omega^k = \mu & \text{on } \Gamma \cap \partial {}^{(i)}Y \\ {}^{(i)}\Omega^k \cdot {}^{(i)}\mathbf{n} = 0 & \text{on } \partial C \end{cases}$$

Problem (16) may be solved once for all. Let us associate to its solution the normal heat flux on Γ , defined by: ${}^{(i)}b^k = {}^{(i)}\Theta^k \cdot {}^{(i)}\mathbf{n}$.

Next, let us introduce the linear operator ${}^{(i)}S$, defined on the subdomain ${}^{(i)}Y$, which associates to the prescribed (but unknown) temperature μ of problem (17) its connected normal heat flux on Γ :

$$(18) \quad {}^{(i)}S : \mu|_{\Gamma} \rightarrow {}^{(i)}S(\mu) = [{}^{(i)}\Omega^k \cdot {}^{(i)}\mathbf{n}]|_{\Gamma}$$

Thanks to these quantities the normal heat flux connected to the solution of problem (13) satisfies:

$$(19) \quad [{}^{(i)}\mathbf{q}^k \cdot {}^{(i)}\mathbf{n}]|_{\Gamma} = {}^{(i)}S(\mu) + {}^{(i)}b^k$$

The continuity condition (14) leads then to the interface problem to be solved on Γ which writes:

$$(20) \quad \text{Find } \mu \text{ such that: } {}^{(1)}S(\mu) + {}^{(2)}S(\mu) = -({}^{(1)}b^k + {}^{(2)}b^k)$$

The symmetric, definite positive operator $S = {}^{(1)}S + {}^{(2)}S$ is called the Schur complement operator [8]. It determines the problem to be solved at the interface Γ between the subdomains. This problem is classically solved by use of the iterative preconditioned conjugate gradient algorithm, whereas the problems to be solved in each subdomain (problems 16 and 17) are fruitfully solved by a direct method, such the Cholesky method.

As mentioned above the use of this method for the "in parallel" solution of the cellular problems requires the choice of a subdomain decomposition for the composite's basic cell. Many subdomain decomposition procedures are available [9], [10]. However, in order to obtain an efficient speed-up, this choice has to almost satisfy some principles, such the minimization of the interface problem size and the load-balancing of the tasks on each of the processors used. We shall see hereafter that mechanical phenomena complicate this choice.

APPLICATION OF PARALLELISM

In order to illustrate the means given above for the parallel simulation of damage's propagation in composite structures, we consider two kinds of three-dimensional composites, used at the industrial level as covering materials for aeronautical engines. These materials and the damages which are experimentally observed are now briefly presented.

Syntactic Foam

The first material we consider is a syntactic foam. It consists of an isotropic resin into which nine glass balloons are arranged in a cubic centered network (see fig. 1). Their internal boundaries are assumed to be stress free.

Fig. 1: Geometric arrangement of the syntactic foam and subdomain decomposition

The experimentally-observed damage process in this composite consists of the implosion of the microballoons, and thus their disappearances. In order to simulate this kind of damage we attach to each (say B_i) of these balloons a scalar denoted by D_i which take the value 1 or 0 depending on whether the balloon is broken or not.

The parallel solution of the cellular problems has been carried out thanks to a decomposition in 8 subdomains shown in figure 1. This choice has been directly induced by the geometry of the basic cell. Indeed, it insures the load-balancing of tasks on each of the 8 processors which are allocated to each of the 8 subdomains, and minimize the size of the interface problem to be solved.

The characteristics of this decomposition are presented in figure 2, which points out the number of degrees of freedom (Finite Element Method) for the global and interface problems corresponding to each of the damaged configurations of the composite's basic cell, in the case of the elasticity cellular problems (1).

Fig. 2: Size of the damaged elastic problems

Thanks to this decomposition, the parallel solution of problems (1) on a MIMD machine (KSR1), leads to times savings which appear very good, as figure 3 attests (the C.P.U. times given in this figure correspond to the solution of one cellular problem (1)).

Fig. 3: C.P.U. times for the solutions of one elastic cellular problem

Indeed, from these results, it appears that the times speed-up is around 7 and thus very close to the optimal and maximal one which is equal to 8.

Sewed Layers of Unidirectional Composites

The second composite we have considered, consists in two layers of unidirectional composites, whose orientations are respectively equal to 0 and 90 degrees, held in contact (one hopes so) by a third constituent, perpendicular to them, called in the sequel the "picot".

Due to the different expansion coefficients of the materials of this basic cell, when the structure undergoes a thermo-elastic loading, the damage occurs under the form of debondings between the constituents. We postulate thus three kinds of defects which are modelled by cavities (denoted by C_i in figure 4) with zero thickness and whose lengths are denoted by L_i . These cavities respectively model the debondings appearing at the interface between the layers and the picot and between the layers themselves.

Fig. 4: Basic cell of the sewed composite - Location and geometric modelization of damages

We associate to these defects three damage parameters defined as follows:

$$(21) \quad D_1 = \frac{L_1}{h_1} \quad D_2 = \frac{L_2}{h_2} \quad D_3 = \frac{L_3}{R}$$

where h_1 , h_2 and R respectively denote the thicknesses of the layer number 1, number 2 and the radius of the picot.

Unlike the syntactic foam considered before, the choice of a subdomain decomposition for the basic cell of this composite is not straightforward, because of its geometry and the presence of damages. This is the reason why we have considered two subdomain decompositions. The first one consists of 20 subdomains whose boundaries coincide with the debondings between the composite's constituents (the degrees of freedom located at the debondings belong thus to the problem to be solved at the interface Γ). The second one consists of 8 subdomains whose boundaries, a priori, do not coincide with the damages localizations. The main disadvantage of the first decomposition stems from the bad load-balancing it induces, whereas the second insures a good load-balancing. Let us lastly note that both decompositions lead to some "floating" subdomains (the local problems such (17) do not admit an unique solution); this fact requires the use of a particular preconditioner technique. We used to this purpose the "Coarse Neumann" [11] and "Neumann-Neumann" preconditioners [12].

Fig. 5: Decompositions in 8 and 20 subdomains

The characteristics of both decompositions are presented on the following figure, for two particular states of damage of the composite's basic cell:

Fig. 6: Size of the elastic problems

We report in figure 7 the C.P.U. times consumed for the solution of one elastic cellular problem by use of these two decompositions and the two preconditioning techniques.

Starting from these results it first appear that, from the point of view of parallelism, the "Coarse Neumann" preconditioner lead to better times savings than the "Neumann-Neumann".

From the times savings point of view, the decomposition in 8 subdomains leads to a speed-up around 6, whereas the decomposition in 20 conducts to a speed-up which is only around 4 (the best are respectively 8 and 20). These results clearly assert that load-balancing is an essential "pre-requisite" for the obtention of good times-savings in parallel, even if it is very difficult to realize this task in case of heterogenous and damaged structures.

Once this choice has been made, the results presented in the case of these two applications, clearly show that parallelism and the methodology used, are powerful.

CONCLUSION

Thanks to the use of the homogenization technique and a subdomain decomposition technique, a computational strategy and a parallel numerical tool have been made available for the simulation of damage's propagation in composite materials. They enable to obtain appreciate times-savings in most cases. However, the results presented in this paper, clearly show that the problem of the choice of a well-suited subdomain decomposition for the composite's representative volume element, remains to be solved, even if the times-savings we have obtained are very encouraging.

In order to allow for the proposed modelization of damage's evolution in composite materials, to fully reveal its potentialities, the work, which has began consists in developing a parallel strategy for the solution of the nonlinear, time-dependent, macroscopic problem.

Fig. 7: C.P.U. times for the solutions of one elastic cellular problem versus subdomain decomposition and preconditioning technique

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